

ISOLATE AND DIAGNOSE SOME GERMS FOR URINARY TRACT INFECTION VARIABLES AND DETERMINE OUR ABILITY TO RESIST ANTIBIOTICS IBN AL-BALADI TEACHING HOSPITAL, BAGHDAD GOVERNORATE

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Abstract: The research included a study in isolating some types of bacteria for germs and fluctuations of urinary tract infection cases among patients admitted to Ibn Al-Baladi Teaching Hospital, Baghdad Governorate, where three types of bacteria were isolated for variables of urinary tract infection cases from urine samples taken from patients with urinary tract infection of both sexes and of different ages. It was diagnosed through morphological, culture and biochemical characteristics, if (40) isolates of this bacterium were diagnosed from (90) patients. Where the study showed that the highest rate of infection was for the type *Proteus mirabilis*, which amounted to (80%), while the rate of infection with the type *Pr. Vulgaris* (30%) These two types are widespread, especially in complex urinary tract injuries resulting from the presence of imbalances in structure and function or in patients exposed to catheterization, The type *penneri Pr.* has formed (20%) and is limited in prevalence and appears in certain disease conditions. Where our antibiotic resistance capabilities were determined, as they showed high sensitivity to Trimethoprim and Ciprofloxacin antibiotics while showing resistance to Ampicillin and Trimethoprim, so the research found the relationship of diagnosing cases in isolating some types of germs to the requirements of urinary tract infection cases and the extent to which their ability to resist antibiotics is determined in patients with structural and functional impairments in the urinary tract.

Introduction:

Joined the genus fluctuates Proteaeae to the *Proteus* tribe and belongs to the family of intestinal bacteria, which produces members of the enzyme Phenylalanine deaminase and consists of a group of microorganisms non-fermented lactose sugar, members of this genus appear phenomenon of swarming on solid media, which is the characteristic of its species (Penner, 1981) and the word *Proteus* means fluctuation in form launched by the researcher, Hauser and includes this genus currently four types, namely *Pr. Myxofaciens*, *Pr. Vulgaris*, *Pr. Mirabilis* and *Pr. Penneri* (Holt et al., 1994) species of the genus Variables are found in soil, water and fecal contaminated material. It is a common cause of urinary tract infection, as the urinary tract is one of those very familiar sites for bacterial infections. (Cook et al.,1995).

Urinary tract infections are divided into two main categories, the first is called uncomplicated, most of which arises from *Escherichia coli* pathogen UPEC, as it occurs in individuals who do not suffer from infections and without systemic symptoms that would make them more predisposed to bacterial infection, and in most cases they respond to antibiotic treatment, while the second group is called complex in patients with dysfunction in the structure and function of the urinary tract, as well as its occurrence in immunocompromised patients, as it is antibiotic therapy Vitality is less impactful. (Foxman et al., 1995)

Pr. Mirabilis is one of the most important causes of urinary tract infection, as well as kidney stones and bladder and is repeated in people with anatomical and functional abnormalities in the urinary tract or in those who have undergone catheterization. (Mobley et al., 1994) (Herias et al., 1997)

The urinary tract infection is treated in uncomplicated and complex cases with short- or long-term prescriptions of antibiotics, and in recent years there has been an increase in resistance to various antibiotics by the causative agents of infection. (Huovinen et al., 1995)

Materials:

The study was conducted on (70) samples taken from people with urinary tract infection of both sexes and different ages and those admitted to Ibn Al-Baladi Teaching Hospital, Sadr City, Baghdad Governorate.

Screening tests:

Implantological and morphological qualities:

Simple and differential food media prepared by Oxoid and BioMerieux were used, namely nutritious broth medium, nutritious agar medium, McConki agar, blood agar medium and Muller-Hinton medium. The samples were planted directly on the medium of the maconki agar and incubated at (37) °C for 24 hours, then (2-3) non-fermented colonies of lactose sugar were isolated from each sample in a pure manner on the nutrient and blood agar medium. The Gram dye was performed to confirm that the isolated spores were negative for Gram dye and to observe the shape of the cells.

Biochemical tests:

Biochemical tests were carried out to diagnose this bacterium and to determine its types, especially the type Pr. vulgaris and the type Pr. penneri for the great similarity between them and the technique was used. Macfaddin, 1985 and type AP120E processed by the French company BioMerieux. (Baron and Finegold, 1990) were also used for diagnosis, confirmatory and performed at Ibn Al-Baladi Teaching Hospital, Sadr City, Baghdad Governorate.

Antibiotic allergy test:

Sensitivity testing was conducted for (11) types of antibiotics obtained in the form of ready-made tablets from Oxoid and others were prepared in the laboratory by the method of wet tablets) (Cruickshank, 1975) so that the tablets contained the globally used concentrations of antibiotics and as recommended by the World Health Organization (Vandepitte et al., 1991)

Antibiotic sensitivity was determined by the method of Zikra Salim Ali et al. (Bauer et al., 1966) modified and prescribed by the World Health Organization (Vandepitte et al., 1991) where (3-5) pure colonies were transferred using a vaccination needle to a test tube containing (5 cm³) sterile physiological saline, the density of the bacterial suspension was controlled with the standard Macfarland Tube No. 1 test tube prepared from the addition of (0.6 cm³) of barium chloride solution and then the completion of Hajj to (10 cm³) by adding (1%) acid, Sulfuric containing an approximate number of (1×10⁸) cells/cm³.

The bacterial suspension was deployed with a sterile cotton swab on the surface of the center of Muller-Hinton Agar, the dishes were left for (3-5) minutes for imbibation to occur, and then the antibiotic tablets were installed using sterile tongs, the dishes were incubated at a temperature of (37) degrees Celsius for 24 hours, after which the diameter of the inhibition area of each tablet was measured and compared with what was stated in the World Health Organization measurements. (Vandepitte et al., 1991)

The following antibiotics were used:

Gentamycin, ******(5 µg) Ciprofloxacin, ******(50 µg) Carbencillin, ******(10 µg) Ampicillin, ******(30 µg) Chloramphenicol, ******(30 µg) Tetracycline, ******(10 µg) Tobramycin, ******(10 µg) (300 Nitrofuration, ******(25 µg) Trimethoprim **·** ******)5 µg) Rifampicin, ******(30 µg) Nalidixic acid . µg)

Findings:

Isolation of the volatile germ from cases of urinary tract infection:

In this study, (20) isolated from the bacteria of variables taken from the administration of (70) patients, and Table (1) shows the isolated types and their percentages.

Table 1. Isolated species and their percentages

No.	Germs Types	Isolated germs	%
1	Proteus mirabilis	14	70
2	Proteus vulgaris	4	20
3	Proteus penneri	2	10
	Total	20	100

With regard to the incidence of urinary tract infection and the age of patients, the study showed that this germ infects the urinary tract of young and old, i.e. of different ages, while sex has been observed that the rate of infection of females is higher than males as shown in Table (2).

Table (2) The origin of the types of bacteria of isolated variables with some important characteristics

No.	Age	gender	Sample	Disease		Proteus
1	23	female	urine	Urinary tract infection	+	Pr.mirabilis
2	30	female	urine	Chronic urinary tract infection	+	Pr.mirabilis
3	20	female	urine	Pregnancy with urinary tract infection	-	Pr.mirabilis
4	45	female	urine	Diabetes with chronic urinary tract inflammation	+	Pr. Vlgaris
5	4	female	urine	Urinary tract infection	+	Pr. vlgaris
6	37	female	urine	Urinary tract infection	-	Pr.mirabilis
7	8	female	urine	Diarrhea with urinary tract infection	-	Pr.mirabilis
8	23	Male	urine	Urinary tract infection	-	Pr.mirabilis
9	11	female	urine	Urinary tract infection	-	Pr.mirabilis
10	19	Male	urine	Chronic urinary tract infection	-	Pr.mirabilis
11	27	female	urine	Pregnancy with chronic urinary tract infection	-	Pr.mirabilis
12	33	Male	urine	Catheterization operation	+	Pr.mirabilis
13	39	female	urine	Urinary tract infection	-	Pr.mirabilis
14	40	Male	urine	Chronic urinary tract infection	+	Pr. Vlgaris
15	31	female	urine	Kidney stone urinary tract infection	+	Pr.mirabilis
16	23	Male	urine	Urinary tract infection	+	Pr. Vlgaris
17	3	female	urine	Diarrhea with urinary tract infection	-	Mirabilis
18	9	female	urine	Chronic urinary tract infection	+	Mirabilis
19	6	Male	urine	Urinary tract infection	-	Pr.Penneri
20	7	Male	urine	Ovulation disease with urinary tract inflammation	-	Pr.Penneri

Cultured and microscopic qualities:

Thus, the targeting and isolation and diagnosis of the germ of variables was used medium Akar Almconki to isolate the germ from urine samples, and the initial diagnosis of this germ depends on the appearance of pale colonies on this medium because it is not fermented for lactose sugar and on the medium of blood and nutrient acar showed the phenomenon of ajel. Cram tincture was performed on the obtained clinical isolates and the bacterium appeared as Cram-negative bacilli.

Biochemical tests for sample tests:

API20E (1-2) technology was used to diagnose the volatility germ, as well as additional diagnostic tests. (Ali et al)

Image (1) API 20E Technology for the Diagnosis of Volatility Bacterial Isolates, *Proteus mirabilis* type

Image (2) API 20E for the Diagnosis of Volatility Bacterial Isolates, *Proteus vulgaris* Type

Antibiotic sensitivity test for sample members:

Figure (1) shows that the types of bacteria fluctuates showed a variation in their sensitivity to antibiotics, as they were resistant to a number of antibiotics while showing little or no resistance to a number of other antibiotics, the results showed that the bacteria were highly resistant to Trimethoprim and Ampicillin antibiotics by (90% and 85%) respectively, while the bacteria were moderately sensitive to antibiotics Nitrofurantoin and Gentamycin and at rates of (55%, 50%) respectively, while the bacteria were towards antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Tobramycin (100%, 90%) respectively.

Figure (2) Allergy and resistance of the germ of variables to antibiotics.

Discussion:

Urinary tract infection is of great importance at present because it arises as model systems for studying the relationship between the host and the microorganism that would clarify new insights into the formative

origin of urinary tract infection (Muhldorfer et al., 2001). The hospital, which has been subjected to catheter operations, as it begins to settle the ureter and this results in bacteriuria, This infection can infect the kidneys causing pyelonephritis (Collee et al., 1996) (Zunino et al., 1999; Liaw et al., 2000) agreed with the current study of the emergence of this type and a high rate, as indicated by (Koneman et al., 1997) in the isolation of the type *Pr. vulgaris* and frequently from patients with urinary tract infections who are immunocompromised, especially those who receive repeated doses of antibiotics, as well as the isolation of the type *Pr. penneri* from a child with leukemia, as this type causes a case of bacteremia After penetrating the intestine and forming abscesses under the skin, which confirms the ability to invade this germ. (Thikra Salim Ali et al). (Warren,1996) indicated that about 10-20% of women and 12% of men suffer from acute urinary tract infections. And that these cases may develop causing sepsis, especially in cases of nosocomial infections, and the current study came in line with what the researcher pointed out. (Warren, 1996) in a higher incidence of females than males. Cases of urinary tract infections with the germ of variables may be attributed to the possession of many virulence factors, including the production of the enzyme urease, which decomposes urea into ammonia, and the presence of these unusual amounts of ammonia in the urine, especially in the bladder, may encourage the precipitation of urinary phosphate, which causes the formation of phosphate stones (Semior, 1999).

As well as the invasion of germs and their adhesion to the epithelial membrane, the spores of fluctuations are characterized by movement and rapid spread in the presence of flagella and possession of hemolysin, which is one of the main factors of virulence of this germ. (Allison et al., 1992).

Clinical symptoms such as pyelonephritis and kidney abscess, as well as other factors such as gender, age, predisposition to illness and pregnancy, are factors influencing antibiotic treatment and duration of treatment (Huovinen et al., 1996), which lead to the emergence of strains resistant to many types of antibiotics as well as the indiscriminate use of antibiotics. The current study agreed with Bush et al. (1995) that the bacterium showed sensitivity to the antibiotic while it was moderately sensitive to the antibiotic and Nitrofurantoin Ciprofloxacin and was resistant to the antibiotic Ampicillin.

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